

Zero-Shot Embedded Neural Architecture Search for On-board Satellite Tasks & Hardware Accelerators

Chetan Kadway, Shalini Mukhopadhyay*, Syed Mujibul Islam, Abhishek Roy Choudhury, Swarnava Dey, Sounak Dey, Arijit Mukherjee, Arpan Pal

Embedded Devices & Intelligent Systems, TCS Research, Kolkata, India

Embedding Artificial Intelligence (AI) onboard satellites is becoming increasingly important in the field of SpaceTech where radiation hardened Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) hardware accelerators are becoming popular to run machine learning and deep learning workloads for benefits like optimizing transmission bandwidth utilization and real-time insights. In current practice, designing such ML/DL models requires experts in neural network design, geo-spatial imaging, and embedded systems. Additionally, the task of migrating such models to a different hardware accelerators platform typically requires significant effort to design and re-train the model. This paper shows how a Zero-Shot heuristic can be used to speed-up reinforcement learning based Neural Architecture Search (NAS) to generate tiny but accurate multi-objective models for cloud cover detection. We achieve a 15x reduction in search time, improved latency and energy consumption, to find task and hardware specific model as compared to a handcrafted model.

Index terms – Satellite, on-board AI, Neural Architecture Search, Reinforcement Learning, TinyML, AutoML, Neuromorphic, Cloud Cover, low power, low latency.

1 Introduction

The vast expanse of space offers a wealth of information critical for scientific discovery, environmental monitoring, and communication infrastructure. To unlock this potential, space agencies and private companies are increasingly turning to embedding intelligence directly on-board satellites. This paradigm shift represents a significant advancement over traditional approaches that rely solely on ground-based processing. A key enabler for on-board intelligence is the growing availability of Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) neural network accelerators specifically designed for the harsh environment of space. These COTS neural network accelerators offer the necessary processing power and efficiency to run sophisticated AI algorithms onboard satellites while maintaining

power and size constraints. At present, there exist two major trends of deploying AI/ML/DL models onboard satellites: (i) Prepare ARD (Analytics Ready Data, e.g. L1C & L2A data of Sentinel-2) onboard satellite, then feed ARD to AI models. (ii) End-to-end AI models applied directly to RAW data itself.

Embedding intelligence on satellites brings several compelling benefits [1, 2]: (i) *Reduced Downlink Data Volume*: By processing data onboard, satellites can discard unusable images with significant cloud cover, dramatically reducing the amount of data transmitted back to Earth. This translates to significant savings in bandwidth and transmission time. (ii) *Prioritized Data Transmission*: On-board processing can identify and prioritize high-value data, such as images with clear skies or those containing features of immediate interest. This prioritization ensures that critical information reaches ground stations promptly. (iii) *Real-Time Alerts and Insights*: By analyzing data onboard, satellites can generate real-time alerts and meta-data summarizing key findings. This allows for faster decision-making and more efficient mission control.

Examples of on-board satellite data processing tasks that can significantly benefit from embedded intelligence include: (i) *Cloud Cover Detection*: intelligently filtering out cloud-obscured images to optimize data transmission and storage [3, 4]. (ii) *Image Compression*: Ever-increasing resolution of satellite imagery creates massive data streams. Deep learning-based compression techniques, both lossless [5] and lossy, can be embedded onboard to significantly optimize the data transmission to Earth. This saves valuable bandwidth and reduces onboard storage requirements. (iii) *Object Detection*: Identifying objects of interest onboard allows for quicker response (e.g., ships in maritime boundaries, land border surveillance). (iv) *Change Detection*: Real-time analysis of changes in land cover or infrastructure can provide valuable insights for environmental monitoring and disaster management (e.g., wildfires, volcanic eruptions). (v) *Anomaly Detection*: Onboard anomaly detection can

*Author E-Mail: shalini.mukhopadhyay@tcs.com

identify unexpected events like equipment malfunctions using satellite telemetry, allowing for preventative maintenance or corrective actions.

While traditional hand-crafted AI models have achieved success in various computer vision tasks, their application to satellites faces significant challenges. One major hurdle is the need for extensive domain expertise to effectively pre-process data, design task-specific neural networks and perform optimization for deployment to target hardware platforms. This workflow necessitates translating the domain knowledge into appropriate network architectures, hyperparameter settings and hardware-specific deployment optimization, a process that can be time-consuming and error-prone. Manually finding the optimal configuration for each combination of these factors is a complex and resource-intensive task, especially considering the evolving nature of satellite data and hardware capabilities. Research by Zoph et al. (2016) [6] and Tan et al. (2019) [7] highlight these challenges and emphasize the need for AutoML approaches like Neural Architecture Search (NAS).

This paper presents Zero-Shot Embedded Neural Architecture Search (Zero-Shot eNAS), a NAS framework based on Deep-Q-Learning. Zero-Shot eNAS is a training free NAS that utilises a modified hamming distance [8] based heuristic function to score and find pareto-optimal neural network architecture sampled from task and hardware specific search space. The main contribution of Zero-Shot eNAS in this paper are as follows:

- Proposes a modified hamming distance-based heuristic function and a sigmoid-based multi-objective RL reward function that can adapt to variety of data, task & target hardware combinations. Hamming distance-based zero-shot heuristics functions make our NAS training free and drastically reduce search time by at least 95%.
- Zero-Shot eNAS can restrict the search space based on ML task and target deployment hardware. In this paper, we have initialised the search for CNN-based classification on AKIDA AKD1000 neuromorphic processor [9].
- Zero-Shot eNAS finds a pareto-optimal CNN that performs Cloud Cover Detection (patch-level binary classifier) on an AKIDA neuromorphic processor.

2 Related Works

The topic of NAS has been explored with growing interest over the past decade, and several techniques

have been devised to handle the process of architecture design, which is essentially formulated as an optimization problem. Recent approaches consider multi-objective optimization, where the performance metrics of the candidate models denote the different objectives. Reinforcement Learning (RL), Bayesian Optimization (BO), and Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) are some of the noteworthy techniques that have been applied over the years. Some of these works are Baker et al. (2016) [10], one of the earliest approaches on RL-based NAS, Real et al.(2017) [11] presenting an evolutionary algorithm for NAS, with several other novel techniques over the years, presented in the papers [12–15].

The works [16, 17] present an RL-based Neural Architecture Framework to perform multi-objective architecture synthesis for tiny, resource-constrained devices. These papers primarily focus on wearable-based time series classification tasks such as ECG classification and smoking activity detection from IMU and PPG signals. In some more recent approaches, the differentiable architecture search-based methods [18] have gained research interest and focus due to the unique way of search-space representation it presents, solving the optimization problem in differentiable form and increased GPU efficiency. These techniques have also been combined and applied with novel design approaches [19, 20]. Today, many such design and optimization techniques have reported high-performance outcomes across various use cases in image classification, time series classification, and other deep learning tasks.

3 Zero-Shot eNAS Framework

Neural Architecture Search has 3 main components namely Search Space, Search Strategy and Evaluation Strategy. These 3 components map to components of the RL system namely Environment, Agent & Reward function, respectively. The Deep-Q agent of our Zero-Shot eNAS depends on a ϵ -greedy policy to sample neural network architectures in each episode from task & hardware-specific search space. The sampled model is then evaluated on various performance metrics, then these metrics collectively contribute to reward function calculation. The sampled architecture and reward function score are stored in Deep-Q RL agent memory so that it can learn and find Pareto-optimal network architectures that balance all performance metrics depending on their weightage.

$$R = \frac{\sum_i w_i \sigma(z_i^{max}) + \sum_j w_j \sigma(-z_j^{min})}{\sum_i w_i + \sum_j w_j}, z_{kpi} = w_{kpi} * \frac{P_{kpi}}{P_{kpi}^{scale}} + C \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Scatter plot of Reward Score Vs Individual KPI (performance metrics) used for multi-objective optimization.

Algorithm 1: Zero-Shot eNAS Algorithm

```

Data: total_episodes, explore_episodes
Result: Modelbest_reward

search_space ← SearchSpace(task, hardware);
rl_policy ← εGreedyPolicy(ε, search_space);
evaluator ← RewardEval(KPIconstraints);
rl_agent ← DQNAgent(alpha, gamma);

Ecurr ← 1;
Etotal ← total_episodes;
Eexplore ← explore_episodes;

while Ecurr ≠ Etotal do
    model ← rl_policy.new_model()
    if model is not duplicate then
        eval_metrics ← evaluator.eval(model);
        rl_agent.memorize(model, eval_metrics);
    end
    if Ecurr == Eexplore then
        evaluator.calibrate_kpi(rl_agent);
        for all models in agent memory do
            R ← evaluator.reward(eval_metrics)
            rl_agent.memorize(model, R);
        end
        rl_agent.train_dqn_model();
    end
    if Ecurr > Eexplore then
        R ← evaluator.reward(eval_metrics);
        rl_agent.memorize(model, R);
        rl_agent.train_dqn_model();
        rl_policy.decay_epsilon();
    end
    Ecurr ← Ecurr + 1;
end

Modelbest_reward ← rl_agent.best_model();
Train Modelbest_reward on full training set;
return Modelbest_reward;
    
```

Here, R is the reward function equation-1 that maps P_{kpi} performance metrics to a reward value between $[0,1]$. Our contribution is modifying the hamming distance-based zero-shot heuristic function to scale it between 0 to 1 bounds so that it becomes convenient to use it in the NAS reward function. The Hamming distance-based metric can score the representational power of a neural network in one forward pass over training data, eliminating the requirement to train the models in each episode of RL-based NAS. w_{kpi} are weightage for each KPI metric, they control both the slope of the sigmoid function and the contribution of each KPI metric to the total reward value R . P_{kpi}^{pscale} are calculated as a percentile of metric values of all models generated during $E_{explore}$ episodes. w_i and w_j are weight values for each P_{kpi} , depending on if it needs to be maximized or minimized respectively.

$$K_H = \begin{pmatrix} N_A - d_H(c_1, c_1) & \dots & N_A - d_H(c_1, c_N) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ N_A - d_H(c_N, c_1) & \dots & N_A - d_H(c_N, c_N) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$K = \sum_l K_H^l \quad A = K / \max(K)$$

Here, K_H is a $N \times N$ matrix for each hidden layer H , each row corresponds to hidden layer representation similarity of i^{th} sample in training subset to all others. N_A is number of neurons in hidden layer H and d_H calculates hamming distance between hidden layer activation of two samples. After summation of K_H across all layers and normalizing using max value of K , we get A matrix. Formula P for Pearson correlation coefficient [21] maps the matrix A to score between $[0,1]$, such that high values indicates high representational capacity of neural network (high probability to achieve high accuracy after training). It indicate high diagonal values & low off-diagonal values in A , i.e. dissimilar hidden layer representations for each data-point. Let $\vec{1}$ be the N -dim vector of all ones, and

let $Z_+ = (1, 2, \dots, N)$ and $Z_+^2 = (1^2, 2^2, \dots, N^2)$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \vec{1} \cdot A \cdot (\vec{1})^T & \sum xy &= Z_+ \cdot A \cdot (Z_+)^T \\ \sum x &= Z_+ \cdot A \cdot (\vec{1})^T & \sum y &= \vec{1} \cdot A \cdot (Z_+)^T \\ \sum x^2 &= Z_+^2 \cdot A \cdot (\vec{1})^T & \sum y^2 &= \vec{1} \cdot A \cdot (Z_+^2)^T \\ P &= \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2} \sqrt{n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}} \end{aligned}$$

4 Experimental Setup

4.1 Dataset & Pre-processing

We use the 38-Cloud dataset [22, 23] which contains 384x384 patches taken from 18 high-resolution Landsat-8 scene images, roughly of size 8000x8000 pixels. This dataset contains images with 4 bands (Red, Green, Blue, and Near Infrared) at 30-meter spatial resolution. Dataset has 8400 training patches and 9201 testing patches with corresponding pixel-level binary cloud mask. For patch-level cloud cover detection in this paper, we have further cropped the 384x384 patches into 32x32 patches with only 3 bands (Red, Green, and Blue). Each of the 32x32 patches is either labelled CLEAR or CLOUDY if the cloud cover percentage is between (0,45] and (45,100] respectively.

4.2 Patch-level Cloud Cover Detection

Cloud Cover Detection is a pixel-level segmentation problem, but at its core requires us to perform two sub-tasks, i.e. cloud localisation and cloud cover percentage estimation. Moreover, AKIDA NSoC imposes certain compatibility checks before a CNN can be mapped to AKD1000, therefore we choose a patch-to-patch class binary classifier which helps us build a CNN that complies with AKIDA hardware constraints and balances the triage of accuracy, latency and power. Hence, we initialise our NAS search space with AKIDA conversion-compatible layer blocks that comply to CNN design constraints in terms of input shape, supported layers, layer orderings and layer hyper-parameters.

4.3 Hardware & Software Used

Neural Architecture Search, CNN training and SNN conversion are performed on a Nvidia A5500 GPU system with 24GB VRAM. We use Brainchip's CNN2SNN conversion toolkit [24] and Akida MetaTF 2.6.0 to deploy SNN models onto Raspberry Pi-based Akida development kit (Broadcom quad-core ARM Cortex -A72 CPU, 8GB RAM, AKD1000

@300MHz neuromorphic processor). CNN2SNN conversion toolkit helps us create SNNs that are structurally and functionally equivalent to the NAS found CNN. Three main steps of CNN2SNN conversion flow are: (i) Conversion compatibility check & training of CNN. (ii) Post Training Quantization and Quantization Aware training. (iii) SNN conversion and deployment to AKD1000 NSoC. Other software versions used are Python 3.9 and TensorFlow 2.11.1.

5 Results & Discussion

As seen from Table 1, it took many attempts of full network training to fine-tune the network architecture. Comparatively, our Zero-Shot eNAS tool 15x less time to find a similar network architecture with comparable pixel-wise accuracy and mean IoU. NAS found model took slightly less energy and latency for a 384x384 test patch. We have used 3 performance metrics to score NAS-generated models using the reward function, the hamming distance-based metric is supposed to be maximized whereas Multiply Accumulate Count (MAC) & Neural Processing Units (NPU consumed after deploying to AKD1000) are supposed to be minimized. As seen from Figure 1, the best NAS found model can correctly balance the KPI of our reward function.

Metrics	Handcrafted Model	Best NAS Model
Pixel Accuracy	91.22	90.75
Mean IoU	81.40	80.27
Latency (ms/patch)	144.69	118.51
Energy (mJ/patch)	0.397	0.274
Search Time (Hours)	16.00	1.15

Table 1: Performance metrics comparison between handcrafted and NAS generated patch-level binary classification model for cloud cover detection.

6 Conclusion & Future Work

In this paper, we introduce Zero-Shot eNAS for space applications, especially for cloud cover detection, with hardware-specific deployment on AKIDA AKD1000 neuromorphic processor. Our reward function uses modified hamming distance based heuristic function provides a robust metric, which in combination with other constraints, reduces the search time by an order of 15x. For more complex tasks requiring complex bigger networks, search time savings will be even higher. Further advancements in such Zero-Shot heuristic based NAS means savings in both time & compute requirements. In future work, we intend to conduct extensive study of our Zero-Short eNAS applied to various combinations of datasets, tasks and target hardware for space qualified hardware accelerators.

References

1. Denby, B. & Lucia, B. in *Proceedings of the Twenty-Fifth International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems* 939–954 (Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3373376.3378473>.
2. Arechiga, A. P., Michaels, A. J. & Black, J. T. *Onboard Image Processing for Small Satellites* in *NAECON 2018 - IEEE National Aerospace and Electronics Conference* (2018), 234–240.
3. Giuffrida, G. *et al.* Cloudscout: a deep neural network for on-board cloud detection on hyperspectral images. *Remote Sensing* **12**, 2205 (2020).
4. Kadway, C., Dey, S., Mukherjee, A., Pal, A. & Bézard, G. *Low Power Low Latency Cloud Cover Detection in Small Satellites Using On-board Neuromorphic Processors* in *2023 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)* (2023), 1–8.
5. Kahali, S. *et al.* *Low-Power Lossless Image Compression on Small Satellite Edge using Spiking Neural Network* in *2023 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)* (2023), 1–8.
6. Zoph, B. & Le, Q. V. Neural architecture search with reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1611.01578* (2016).
7. Tan, M. *et al.* Mnasnet: Platform-aware neural architecture search for mobile. *Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition 2019-June* (2019).
8. Mellor, J., Turner, J., Storkey, A. & Crowley, E. J. *Neural Architecture Search without Training* in *International Conference on Machine Learning* (2021).
9. Brainchip. *Akida AKD1000 Ref SoC* <https://brainchip.com/akida-neural-processor-soc/>. 2024.
10. Baker, B., Gupta, O., Naik, N. & Raskar, R. *Designing Neural Network Architectures using Reinforcement Learning* (2016).
11. Real, E. *et al.* *Large-scale evolution of image classifiers* in *International conference on machine learning* (2017), 2902–2911.
12. Hutter, F., Kotthoff, L. & Vanschoren, J. *Automated machine learning: methods, systems, challenges* (Springer Nature, 2019).
13. Li, C. *et al.* *Block-wisely supervised neural architecture search with knowledge distillation* in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (2020), 1989–1998.
14. Zhang, M., Li, H., Pan, S., Chang, X. & Su, S. *Overcoming multi-model forgetting in one-shot NAS with diversity maximization* in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (2020), 7809–7818.
15. Ren, Y., Li, L., Yang, X. & Zhou, J. *Autotransformer: Automatic transformer architecture design for time series classification* in *Pacific-Asia Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* (2022), 143–155.
16. Mukhopadhyay, S., Dey, S., Ghose, A., Singh, P. & Dasgupta, P. *Generating Tiny Deep Neural Networks for ECG Classification on Micro-Controllers* in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications Workshops and other Affiliated Events (PerCom Workshops)* (2023), 392–397.
17. Sharma, V., Mukhopadhyay, S., Bhattacharya, S., Dey, S. & Ghose, A. *PuffConv: A System for Online and On-device Puff Detection for Smoking Cessation* in *Proceedings of WRISTSENSE 2023: Ninth Workshop on sensing systems and applications using wrist worn smart devices* (2023).
18. Liu, H., Simonyan, K. & Yang, Y. *Darts: Differentiable architecture search*. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.09055* (2018).
19. Liang, H. *et al.* *Darts+: Improved differentiable architecture search with early stopping*. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.06035* (2019).
20. Chu, X., Zhou, T., Zhang, B. & Li, J. *Fair darts: Eliminating unfair advantages in differentiable architecture search* in *European conference on computer vision* (2020), 465–480.
21. Wikipedia. *Pearson Correlation Coefficient* https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pearson_correlation_coefficient#For_a_sample. 2024.
22. Mohajerani, S. & Saeedi, P. *Cloud-Net: An End-To-End Cloud Detection Algorithm for Landsat 8 Imagery* in *IGARSS 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium* (July 2019), 1029–1032.
23. Mohajerani, S., Krammer, T. A. & Saeedi, P. *"A Cloud Detection Algorithm for Remote Sensing Images Using Fully Convolutional Neural Networks"* in *2018 IEEE 20th International Workshop on Multimedia Signal Processing (MMSP)* (Aug. 2018), 1–5.
24. Brainchip. *CNN2SNN Toolkit* https://brainchip-inc.github.io/akida_examples_2.6.0-doc-1/user_guide/cnn2snn.html. 2024.